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COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING TO TEACH UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

*G'aniyeva Barchinoy Bahrom qizi*¹

¹ Faculty of English Philology teaching, Uzbekistan State World Languages University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Annotation: Although tutoring and literacy language is not a new content for experimenters, it always inspires preceptors and linguists. Among new tutoring approaches, Communicative Language Teaching(CLT) is a tutoring system that emphasizes communicative affair. This approach has been extensively known worldwide since it was first introduced in the 1970s because of the demand for communication chops of language learners. still, there are still numerous issues raised because preceptors are not analogous to this system. In terms of language capability, Verbal aspects like lexis, syntax, phonology and morphology as the central part of learning language, while grammatic, semantic, sociolinguistic andrealistic aspects[1]. Other authors' propositions lead to a new advance in developing communicative language tutoring in tutoring and learning a alternate language[2]. Compared with the Grammar- Translation system, CLT provides learners with further openings to develop their communicative capability and increase the part of learners in tutoring and learning alternate language classroom conditioning, which is hard to find in other old tutoring styles. This paper focuses on the overview of CLT in tutoring English as a alternate language. In particular, it summarises the advantages and disadvantages of CLT comparing with old tutoringstyles, current trends of CLT, obstacles in applying CLT in the university environment. Since also, it helps preceptors have a better understanding of CLT and the composition also suggests counteraccusations of tutoring English with CLT in the university environment, including designing classroom conditioning and motivating scholars.

Keywords: Communicative language teaching, university students, tutoring, verbal aspect, language.

I. INTRODUCTION

English ranks the fourth among languages that have the utmost people officially speak and it's the most popular language for transnational communication. Thus, tutoring and learning English is always a concern by preceptors and experimenters worldwide, especially tutoring English for university scholars entering the pool right after scale. Some people may suppose that university scholars have to be good at English because they've spent seven to further than ten times learning it. Still, in Vietnam and other Asian countries, the English position of university scholars are colorful because of their educational background and capability. Coming from different places, including megacity, country, pastoral area or indeed mountainous vill, utmost of them find English bone of the most grueling subjects although they want to be good at English to find a better job. In general, the issues of scholars in Vietnam are fairly low, which is also set up in other countries like [3,4,5,6]. There are other reasons to explain the poor performance of university scholars in alternate language literacy like schoolteacher's tutoring capability and quality, lack of factual chance of communicating with native people in English, which is supported by the exploration of Souriyavongsa et al. in the National University of Laos. Thus, to increase the quality of tutoring and learning English in University, numerous changes in different aspects need to be considered. Tutoring styles should be especially bandied because preceptors typically take the part of educator and directly impact the literacy process in the classroom. English preceptors need applicable tutoring styles to engage and motivate their scholars to ameliorate their English capability. In terms of tutoring system or approach, utmost English preceptors are familiar with traditional tutoring styles like the Grammar Translation system, Direct system, Audiolingual, Community Language Learning, Suggestopia Silent Way, or Total Physical Response. When traditional styles can not satisfy the demand of communication and commerce outgrowth[7], ultramodern tutoring styles have been introduced to meet the need of recent literacy and tutoring English, including CLT, CBI(Content- Grounded Instruction), TBI(Task- Grounded Instruction). CLT, which requires spoken affair, is proving its effectiveness when it meets learners' need for communicative capability. Still, CLT has not veritably popular, especially in the university setting. By synthesising inquiries on CLT, the author wants to find the answer for three main questions. Research questions:

1. What are the advantages of CLT in tutoring and learning English as a alternate language?
2. What are the disadvantages of CLT in tutoring and learning English as a alternate language for university scholars?
3. How to apply CLT effectively in tutoring English as a alternate language in a university environment?

II. LITERARY REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

CLT is the result of new demand in literacy and tutoring English. GMT had been dominant for a long time before the preface of CLT. Numerous linguists claim that learning a language will be more effective when following natural styles. "Religionists in the Natural system argued that a foreign language could be tutored without restatement or the use of the learner's native language if the meaning was conveyed directly through demonstration and action"[8]. Learning a language is effective when learners have further chance exposing to it, using it in real discussion. This process is not veritably different from learning their mamalingo. Thus, the traditional styles that emphasise grammatical aspects and restatement feel not to produce a robotic terrain for learners. CLT is an innovative language tutoring which fosters and encourages learners to use their general knowledge and verbal knowledge to break real tasks like discussion, concession, convert, making a decision, when they mention CLT includes real-life conditioning between groups like concession or commerce[9]. Through real and like-real practice,

learners ameliorate their English capability and are confident to use English to communicate with others.

Being introduced in 1970s, CLT has been considered and accepted in numerous countries[10,11,12]. CLT is an evolution for the traditional tutoring system GTM because it involves meaningful communication and requires communicative input and outgrowth[13]. Learning with traditional styles, scholars may be good at alphabet and vocabulary, but they are not confident to communicate with English speakers because they infrequently have a chance to use their English knowledge in real discussion. English is a language, so if learners do not use it frequently, it's hard for them to memorise vocabulary and without real-life situation practises, their English can not be a tool to communicate, but a subject at academy. CLT as an approach that allows learners to use language to do effects, which means that tasks are seen as generalities, sundries, and meaningful conditioning rather of a particular alphabet point or separated language chops[14]. Five main features of CLT

1. Concentrating on learning to communicate in the target language.
2. Using authentic textbooks in learning conditioning.
3. furnishing openings for learners to develop their language and literacy process.
4. Encouraging particular experience as an essential element for classroom conditioning.
5. trying to connect classroom tasks with outside classroom conditioning[15].

Grounded on these features, four communicative capability of CLT, including 'grammatical capability', 'sociolinguistic capability', 'converse capability', and 'strategic capability' while it into 'organizational capability' and 'realistic capability'[16,17]. CLT principally refers to the capability to use language 'receptively and productively' in real-life situations[18]. CLT aims to exploit the capability to use much different knowledge, both general and verbal, into meaningful tasks and conditioning which pretend real-life situations in order to develop learners' language aspects similar as maintaining discussion despite the limitation in language knowledge, using language for different purposes and functions, using and understanding different types of textbooks, using applicable language for a different setting like formal and informal situations[19]. CLT system is also a good way to enrich learner's general knowledge like Doughty and Long countries, "new knowledge is better integrated into long-term memory, and easier recaptured if tied to real-world events and conditioning". Authentic accoutrements with tremendous knowledge of culture and different aspects from wisdom to diurnal life of numerous different nations and indeed the macrocosm give learners streamlined information necessary for them to be successful in their work and life.

CLT is one of the most effective styles in tutoring and learning an alternate language because it provides openings for learners to exercise and ameliorate their communicative capability in pedagogic and real-life situations. Although it has not extensively enforced in university seminaries yet, preceptors and scholars have a positive station towards this system because of its benefits. The real practice of CLT in university academy has shown advantages and disadvantages or difficulties both outside and inside the classroom. thus, preceptors need to consider the real situation at their academy to have effective perpetration of CLT classes.

III. RESULTS

Advantages of CLT in teaching and learning English as second language

CLT is considered as the stylish result in perfecting the communicative capability of learners. Grounded on principles of CLT, Five main features of CLT. CLT focuses on communicative input and outgrowth when it requires authentic material, communication between learners, which uses both general

knowledge and verbal knowledge, linking inside the class and the world outside through life- suchlike situations. also, to effectively join CLT conditioning, learners should exploit and develop their sociolinguistic, converse, strategic, and grammatical capability or organizational and realistic capability. As a result, learners acquire the target language effectively in both implicit and unequivocal ways. Another advantage of CLT is the active part of learners in classroom conditioning. In traditional classes, learners passively gain knowledge which substantially comes from their preceptors and given text. It means that good scholars(who follow preceptors and finish all exercises fastening on alphabet and vocabulary) may not be a person who can communicate in English well in real life. They are not familiar with real- life situations and do not have a chance to communicate(like order, bandy, negotiate, complain, or make a decision) with mates. still, CLT conditioning give them numerous openings to « talk in English» and turn their chance of communication into their experience for unborn communication. In fact, in CLT classes, learners are in the part of attendants and the center of the tutoring and literacy process. thus, attending classroom conditioning means learning a language and perfecting their language capability rather of finishing all given exercises. Accordingly, learners have further provocation for language accession. Another inarguable strength of CLT is that it enhances and enriches learners' general knowledge and verbal knowledge anyhow of their language situations. scholars with good English capability and learners with lower position can also learn in CLT classes because CLT conditioning give meaningful tasks and real like situations to develop language aspects, including maintaining discussion for learners with language limitations. Eventually, preceptors get benefits from CLT conditioning, too. To design CLT conditioning, preceptors have to spend time on the medication of material and suitable tasks. And, in classroom conditioning, preceptors as the part of party and runner facilitator directly or laterally attend conditioning so that they've further practice to bettering their tutoring career and also enlarge their knowledge by approaching authentic accoutrements . In general, CLT provides tremendous benefit for both learners and preceptors so that it should be introduced and extensively applied into English classes in the university position for scholars who are just one step to enter life and the pool.

Disadvantages of CLT in teaching and learning English as second language for university students

CLT is originally introduced by native speakers and originally used for native preceptors so that it shows disadvantages when extensively used for tutoring ESL university scholars in other countries, especially Asian countries like Vietnam, Thailand, China, South Korea, Bangladesh, etc. Besides the benefits that CLT brings, several obstacles have been set up in enforcing this system. originally, common conflicts in Asian countries environment beget the limited operation of CLT. Written examinations contribute to CLT's holdback into the real tutoring and literacy process[21,22,23]. Asian education still relies on examinations that are substantially written in written format so that preceptors and scholars pay further attention to passing examinations with flying colours than achieving better communicative capability. thus, at first, CLT seems not too suitable to learn English as a mandatory subject at academy in Asia. still, if being considered in the main purpose of alternate language accession, CLT, with its principle, meets the requirements of communicative affair for scholars and motivates scholars to laboriously attend CLT conditioning. The conflicts between the effectiveness and real environment cause the failure and defer in extensively recrimination of CLT. Secondly, although both preceptors and scholars know the effectiveness of CLT, they are not veritably confident to apply this system. There are a lot of reasons similar as lack of applicable knowledge of CLT[24,25,26], inadequate impulses to encourage preceptor[27], lack of authentic material[28], scholars' vacillation and time constraints[29], language and artistic background of learners, the large size of classes[30,31]. The recrimination of commodity new always encounter difficulties that come from different aspects. In particular, scholars in Asian countries, in particular, with a deep background of culture, defer laboriously attending CLT

conditioning further than Western learners. station is one of the most important factors contributing to the effectiveness of enforcing CLT. Although both preceptors and scholars have a positive station towards CLT, the realperpetration in different settings faces different obstacles. That can be seen as someone sees a beautiful dress but it needsrevision to fit her body well. In western countries, scholars visit a plant, talk with the chairman, or attend realexchanges to learn language and knowledge, whereas, in eastern countries, these real conditioning are smaller and delicate in the organisation.

IV. DISCUSSION

Based on mentioned analysis about the advantages and disadvantages of CLT, the author suggests some implication of CLT in the university context.

Originally, handbooks currently modernize new tutoring styles in their design and content. preceptors with knowledge of CLT can take advantage of the material to produce communication conditioning in class like a problem- working, interview, part- play, conversations, simulation, or information gap exchange. At first, scholars may face a lot of difficulties, but they will soon get familiar with real life practice and ameliorate their communicative capability. In addition, university scholars with a piece of rather wider knowledge than other situations can snappily acclimatize and contribute to CLT classes. ‘ A rule of thumb for authentic material is any material which has not been specifically produced for the purposes of language tutoring’[32]. Learning a language should go with authentic accoutrements that give real information, textbooks written by native authors, real- life reading andharkening material so that learners understand and easily apply their verbal and sociolinguistic chops in the classroom andalso in their future working surrounds. With the development of technology, especially the internet, preceptors can fluently find authentic material online and in real life. Learning societies through authentic material is also veritably necessary because it enlarges pupil’s knowledge and it's like good medication for them to integrate into a different culture of the places they may visit. thus, scholars can also find comfort and familiarity when travelling to other countries or work in English-speaking surroundings because the real situations are not so different from what they approach at university classes.

Secondly, grounded on the English position of scholars, preceptors can apply two main dispatches that Including functional communication conditioning to develop specific language chops or functions and social commerce conditioning to design discussion or discussion conditioning that bear further knowledge of the language[33]. As a result, preceptors can give new knowledge in implicit and unequivocal ways to produce a natural literacy terrain for their classes and the tutoring and literacy will be more intriguing than when the schoolteacher takes the center part in class.

Thirdly, in term of the part of the schoolteacher in CLT class, preceptors should flexibly apply CLT in their classes and concentrate on particular aspects of communicative capability at each time. scholars need to learn numerous chops rather of speaking only during the course[34]. Thus, preceptors should be flexible in the perpetration of CLT system. In addition, CLT for different classes should be applicable like assignments for English major class should be designed suitably for developing specific chops(listening, speaking, reading, or jotting), integrated subjects(restatement, interpretation), or English for a specific purpose(business English, English for mastermind, etc.) while assignments fornnon-major classes should concentrate more on communicativecapability and substantially develop speaking capability because their outgrowth requires the ignorance further than the delicacy like major bone.

V. CONCLUSION

“Styles should not be understood as conventions for classroom geste and assessed on preceptors as a strict set of procedures to follow[35]. Rather, they should be used to help" expand a schoolteacher's force ofways" and" give an avenue for professional growth ”. thus, the overview of CLT, including the

affiliated aspects, obstacles in perpetration, the station of preceptors and learners towards it, aims to supply a general view as well as encourage English preceptors to acclimatize this system in their university environment. Each system has its strengths and sins, and the realoperation may lead to issues in a particular environment. With its pretensions, main characteristics, and principles, CLT is a good way to foster university scholars' communicative capability. Effective perpetration of CLT can bring a lot of benefits to preceptors and scholars because this system exploits numerous different aspects of language knowledge and general knowledge to enhance sociolinguistic and strategic capability. During the history of CLT, this system causes several difficulties due to the conflicts of environment, schoolteacher and pupil's belief, lack of CLT training, and other minor factors. By synthesizing exploration on CLT in university, the author hopes that university preceptors understand further about CLT and confidently register training course about designing CLT conditioning for their classes. These mentioned operation of CLT system in the university terrain are suggestions and they need farther exploration to test the effectiveness. The composition also suggests that unborn exploration on CLT focuses on scholars' point of view to dissect it from a different perspective to have further results for enforcing CLT effectively in ESL classes in general and in the Asian environment in particular.

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